

Equity renormalization

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Historical data of stock market prices often contain share-splits, obscuring the numerical past in favor of the present; of course, the logarithmic scale does help to equalize somewhat, but it flips the flaw. Let's consider Apple (AAPL) as an example.

The image below charts AAPL daily closing stock price in the top tier, then in log-scale below.

Log-rescaling has indeed revealed more detail prior to 2010 - obscured by the price-splits - but the explosive growth after 2020 is not reflected at all.

Is there a way to renormalize an equity, reducing its dynamic range yet retaining useful features?

Let's first make AAPL complex; with 'dat' a notational stand-in for AAPL:

$\exp(2\pi i \text{dat})$

Now display the argument $\{\arg(\exp(2\pi i \text{dat}))\}$ of the resulting complex stream (see below):

As expected, fold-overs occur whenever the argument exceeds $[-\pi, \pi]$, so let's unwrap this angular output and recover a version of the original data; see below, next page.

In pseudo-code the command is $\text{ren1}=\text{unwrap}(\arg(\exp(2\pi i \text{dat})))$.

Some equalization has taken place, particularly after 2017; for good measure, let's repeat the process on the renormalized equity $ren1$, i.e. $ren2=unwrap(arg(exp(2\pi i ren1)))$.

The outcome shown below does magnify some features after 2005; and repeating this process quite a few times yielded additional detail at each stage, though not convergence.

Another tack is to first reduce the historical data's dynamic range as

$$dyn=(dat-min(dat))/range(dat);$$

then repeat the renormalization process several times; the output is tiered below (bottom, reduced in range), under the historical data; a plethora of volatile behavior is evident, of unclear correlation.

Another way to reduce dynamic range is statistical: $dyn=(dat-mean(dat))/std(dat)$.

Several iterations of the renormalization process produced more new output (tiered below), though no less difficult to interpret.

Yet another approach makes use of spectral analysis.

A (raw) spectrogram of the original unwrapped argument stream is shown in the top tier below, followed by its maximum value.

Smooth this Spectral Maximum with a 10-day window; the result is in the top tier below, usefully confirming (for a change) the onset of growth after 2010: a flat, though jagged, Spectral Maximum.

